

1 **Cellular response to mycobacterial infection.**

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7 We measured total transcription in cells following infection with *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Yersinia*
8 *pseudotuberculosis* to understand the largest transcriptional changes associated with pathogenic
9 mycobacterial infection in humans. We report here specific chemokine activation by *Yersinia*. *Yersinia*
10 infection resulted in robust activation of *Cxcl13*, *Cxcl9* and *Ccl19*. Cells activated *Ido1* in response to
11 *Yersinia* infection.

12 Citations

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